

Chelation and antibiotic activity

Purushottam B. Chakrawarti*

Institute for Excellence in Higher Education, Kaliasot Dam, Kolar Road, Bhopal-462 016, India

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Importance of chelation of antibiotics with the biologically important metal ions during their antibiotic activity has been emphasized in this review. As metal ions have been shown involved practically in every phase of biological activity, like most of the reactions occurring in the biological systems, the action of an antibiotic drug also requires one or other metal ion apart from the reactant substrates and the presence of specific enzymes as catalysts. The voluminous work appearing in the literature on chelation tendency of various antibiotics and also the study of complexation equilibria of ternary systems, involving metal ions and the antibiotic drug in the presence of amino acid fragment of the enzyme or nucleic acid residue, has given useful information for elucidating the molecular mechanism of drug-action. Thus combination of recent experimental and theoretical developments can help to develop innovative strategies for preparing improved and better antibiotics in the light of the chelate hypothesis.

When a metal ion combines with an electron donor the resulting substance is said to be a complex or coordination compound. If the substance, ligand, which combines with the metal contains two or more donor groups forming one or more rings with the metals, the resulting structure is said to be a chelate compound or metal chelate and the ligand is said to be a chelating agent. Metal chelates play important role in biological system in which enzymes are known to be activated by metal ions. The participation of the metalloproteins (which function as metal chelates) in respiratory, photosynthetic, nitrogen fixation, biosynthetic and metabolic processes is essential to the foundation of life¹⁻⁴. Nucleotides as coenzymes in enzymic reactions function only in the form of metal ion complexes⁵⁻⁸. Furthermore, DNA and RNA polymerase are mostly Zn²⁺ metalloenzymes^{9,10}, which generally use the Mg²⁺ complexes of their nucleotide substrates.

The interaction of metal ions with biomolecules and the function of metal ions in physiological systems are very complex, and the precise mechanism of these interactions is almost unknown. It is reported that the activity is a combination of steric, electronic and pharmacokinetic factors and it could be understood in the light of chelation theory^{2,3}. Irrespective of whether a metal ion forms the integral part of the active site of an enzyme, or, the enzyme requires the metal ion as a cofactor for its activity, mixed ligand complexes involving metal ions, enzymes and the substrates are formed in most enzymic reactions. The specific role played by a metal ion in an enzymic reaction is often difficult to elucidate due to the complex nature of the protein structure. Model studies with relatively simple molecules of known structures often yield valuable information that gives clues to the roles of metal ions in many enzymic reactions^{11,12}.

Metals are supposed to serve two purposes : (i) provide proper stereo-chemical orientation and (ii) bring reacting molecules (the enzyme and substrate) closer so that the reaction may occur.

Similar to the enzyme-activity, participation of metal ions during activity of antibiotic drugs has also been shown important. As a matter of fact the action of drug is based on a sequence of chemical events starting when the active agent enters the body and culminating when it eventually reaches the target organ and produces a response. This process is highly complicated and it is by no means obvious to the layman, how and why taking by mouth of an analgesic removes the pain of gout in a toe, whilst the site of action for the drug is the brain. This complex process, however, may be described in three discrete phases : (a) The pharmaceutical phase, (b) The pharmacokinetic phase, and (c) The pharmacodynamic phase. The pharmaceutical phase is concerned with the pharmaceutical availability of the active principle. While the pharmacokinetic phase is concerned with optimisation of biological availability and the pharmacodynamic phase is concerned with the interaction of the active principle with the receptor. This phase is of greatest interest to a medicinal chemist; as it deals with the required biological effect, i.e. the site and the mechanism of drug-action. Biological response of drug is the result of its interaction with the receptor. Receptor may be considered as a locus on the plasmic membrane with a structure which facilitates its preferential and selective contact with the drug molecule (at the surface or inside the cell affected). Recent studies have shown them proteneous in nature, usually a membrane protein. They may be regarded as chemical groups on the receptor (protoplasmic macromolecule) which give recognition site for molecules having specific structure (the drug molecule), i.e. shape of the drug

*Address for communication : A-252, Shahpura, Bhopal-462 016, India.

molecule in three-dimensional space is crucial for union with the receptor; molecules with a fixed conformation may only get fitted in these sites. This suggests that the drug and their receptors share complementary structure, which helps a drug to recognise its receptor (so it is said, receptor response are genetically determined). This is somewhat similar to the lock and key arrangement (*cf.* enzyme-substrate interaction). Binding of active principle to the receptor causes a specific change in the macromolecule (protoplasmic membrane) that triggers a stimulus either directly or indirectly and brings about subsequent sequence of biological events which eventually produces a tissue response. This is true with the drugs being agonist. However, antagonist also binds to the receptor, but is not capable of producing pharmacological response and produces receptor blockage. This is because they have structures similar to the receptor, hence they mimic the activity of the receptor, thus blocking its activity :

Drug response is directly proportional to the receptor occupancy and the interaction is bimolecular, i.e. only one drug molecule (active principle) is required to activate a receptor. The mechanism of drug action depends upon the interactive forces that bind the drug to the receptors. These forces may vary from the rigid covalent bonding to the weak Van der Waals forces.

Interaction of drug and receptor has been a subject of wide speculations. Amongst several possible mechanisms, the most well known are the intercalation mechanism, the electrostatic binding and groove binding. However, various physicochemical methods (including molecular spectroscopy) and biological data (pertaining to molecular biology), in combination with the computer graphics aided molecular modelling have more or less conclusive support to the recent 'chelate hypothesis', that the interaction of drug and receptor understandably takes place in the form of metal-bridged drug-receptor complex (chelate)³. This hypothesis seems to be quite important in the light of the fact that probably all the antimicrobial agents have chelating tendency and the assumption that the activity of an antibiotic agent depends in part, upon their ability to form stable chelates. According to this hypothesis, the drug-receptor interaction may be visualised in one of the two (a) and (b) or both; the equilibria given below :

It is believed that in the pharmaceutical phase the released active-principle (L) reacts with the specific metal ion (M) to form chelate-complex (ML) which is then transported to the target organ where it binds with the receptor (R) forming the hypothetical metal-bridged drug receptor complex (RML); or the active principle (L) after the release from the tablet (or the formulation) transports to the receptor site (R) and binds with it through the metal ion (M) associated with the receptor (ML) resulting in formation of the metal-bridged drug-receptor complex (LMR). Just as mixed ligand complex formation equilibria of metal ion with amino acids and small peptides in the presence of typical ligands provide models for metal-protein interactions in metalloenzymes²; the simplest model of otherwise complex receptor-drug interaction may be the study of a ternary complex, MLA, consisting of metal ion, M^{II}, coordinated by two different ligands, L (the drug) and A, the receptor (the enzyme residue/the nucleic acid base) other than the solvent. Formation, structure, stability and reactivity of such ternary complexes have been studied by many workers¹³⁻¹⁵.

The antibiotic action of transferrin is typical of the possible action of several antibiotics in typing up essential metal ions¹⁶. It is proposed that the transferrin (iron-binding protein, responsible for the transport of iron in higher animals) has larger stability constants towards iron(III) than do the various siderophores (analogous compounds in aerobic microorganisms which solubilize and transport iron(III)). It is thus quite likely that conalbumin (oval transferrin) acts as an antibacterial agent. In the presence of excess conalbumin, bacteria would be iron-deficient since the siderophore cannot compete successfully for the iron. Streptomycin, aspergilliac acid, usnic acid, the tetracyclines, and other antibiotics are known to have chelating properties. Presumably some antibiotics are delicately balanced so as to be able to compete successfully with the metal binding agents of the bacteria while not disturbing the metal processing by the host¹⁷.

The action of the antibiotic need not be a simple competitive one. The chelating properties of antibiotic may be used in transport across membranes or to attach the antibiotic to a specific site from which it can interfere with the growth of bacteria. This seems to give a logical explanation to the drug-receptor interaction. The voluminous work appearing in the literature on chelation tendency of various antibiotics (Table 1) and physicochemical and pharmacological studies of their metal chelates have revealed interesting

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Table 1. Metal chelates of certain antibiotic drugs*

Group Example	Mechanism of action	Active part	Binary chelates	Ternary chelates	Active metal ions	Ref.
(A) Those inhibit cell wall synthesis	Inhibit the terminal cross link of the linear glycopeptides via check of the activity of trans-peptidase enzyme due to structural similarity of these drugs to acyl-d-alanyl-d-alanine	OCN-grouping of β -lactam thiazolidine ring	$1^r-x^b y^b, o, p$ $1^v-x^d, q$ $1^r-x^b, y^b, o, p$ $1^r-x^b-o, p, 3^b$ $1^r-x^b-o, p, 3^b$ $1^r-x^b, o, p$ $1^s-x^b-o, p$ $1^s-x^b, o, p$	- 1^v-x^d - 1^v-x^d 1^r-x^c - 1^r-x^d 1^r-x^d	Cu^{II}, Mn^{II} $Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Ni^{II}$ Mn^{II}, Zn^{II} Cd^{II} $Mg^{II}, Mn^{II}, Zn^{II}$ $Zn^{II}, Co^{II}, Fe^{II}$ Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}	18-22 24, 25 19-22, 23 26-28 29, 30 31 32, 33 34, 35
(B) Those inhibit protein synthesis	Bind to 30S/50S sub-unit of the microbial ribosomes to stop protein synthesis, interfere the binding of new aminoacids to the nascent peptide chain	<i>N</i> -methyl-glycosamine unit COCHC(OH) grouping Hydroxy <i>sec</i> -oxygen and amino nitrogen	$1^{r,s}, 2^l-x^d-o, p, 3^b$ $1^s, 2^l-x^b, o, p, 3^b$ $2^r, y^d$ $1^u-x^b, o, p, 3^b$		$Mn^{II}, Mg^{II}, Zn^{II}$ $Fe^{II}, Mg^{II}, Zn^{II}$ Mg^{II}	36, 37 38, 39 40, 41
(C) Those inhibit nucleic acid synthesis	Bind to deoxyguanosine residue to stop DNA synthesis due to blocking of m-RNA formation	Sulfonamido oxygen and nitrogen of the ring	$1^l-x^b, 2-x^3, 3^b$ $1^l-x^b, 2-x^c$ $1^l-x^b, 2-x^c, 3^b$ $1^r, x^b, y^b, 2-x^c, 3^b$ $2-x^e, 3^b$ $2-x^e$ $2-x^e, 3^b$ $2-x^e$ $2x^c, 3^b$ $2-x^e, 3^b$ $2-x^3, 3^b$ $1^s-x^b, O, p$	1^r-x^c 1^r-x^c 1^r-x^c	Fe^{II}, Co^{II} Zn^{II} Mg^{II} Zn^{II}, Cu^{II} Mg^{II}, Mn^{II} $Zn^{II}, Cu^{II}, Fe^{II}$	42-59 60 61
Ethambutol	CONH-NH ₂ grouping Ethylenedi-amine moiety		$1^s, x^b, O, p$			

* Symbols :

- 1 = Potentiometric studies
- 2 = Spectrophotometric studies
- 3 = Bacteriocidal studies
- o = Octahedral
- p = Distorted octahedral
- q = Sq. planar
- a = (M : L) 1 : 1 chelate
- b = (M : L) 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 chelates
- c = (M : L : A) 1 : 1 : 1; A = aminoacid
- d = (M : L : A) 1 : 1 : 1; A = nucleic acid base
- e = (M : L) 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 2 : 1

- r = $\mu = 0.1 M$ and 30°
- s = $\mu = 0.1 M$ and $25^\circ, 35^\circ$
- t = $\mu = 0.1 M$ and $27^\circ, 37^\circ$
- u = Three ionic concentrations and two temperatures
- v = $\mu = 0.1 M$ and 37°
- x = Bioactive metals
- y = 'a' and 'b' class metals

observations in support of the chelate hypothesis of metal-bridged drug-receptor interaction :

[1] Most of the antibiotics have N, O and S containing groups, situated at the site ideal for formation of strain-free five- or six-membered ring, and give 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (metal : drug) chelates with the biologically important metal ions (e.g. Cu^{II} , Co^{II} , Zn^{II} , Mn^{II} , Mg^{II} and Fe^{II}) mostly in octahedral (or occasionally square-planar) stereochemistry.

It is well known that the heterocyclic compounds (containing potential donor atoms N, S and O) exhibit antibacterial activities due to the presence of multifunctional (heterofunctional) groups. When such heterocyclic ligands are complexed with the metal ions they have enhanced activity^{19,32,34,62,64}. Complexation with metal reduces the polarity of metal ion considerably because of partial sharing of its positive charge with donor groups and delocalization of π -electrons over the whole chelate ring, resulting in high lipid solubility. The rate of antibiotic activity gradually increases with the increase in concentration of the drug ($M : L$, 1 : 2 complexes give higher concentration of the drug at the receptor) and also probably due to combined bioactive effect of metal ion and the ligand present in the complex. One interesting class of heterocycles having O, N and/or S donors are thiazolidines, including β -lactam thiazolidines (e.g. penicillin and cephalosporins), whose enzymatic activity also depends upon their metallation^{3,26-29,64} with the vitally important metal ions.

Drug activity is mainly structurally specific, i.e. dependent upon factors such as the presence or absence of certain groups, intramolecular distances, the shape of molecule and the interaction of the drug with a cellular receptor. The structure-reactivity relationship confirms the assumptions that the active principle of the drugs have the characteristic groups complementary to the structures of the receptors (Table 1), e.g. in penicillins and cephalosporins, the active part is OCN grouping of the β -lactam thiazolidine ring, formed from L-systenine and D-valine. The $\text{O}=\text{C}-\text{N}$ bond in the β -lactam ring is in precisely the same position as the peptide bond in D-alanyl-D-alanine of transpeptidase which splits during transpeptidation. These drugs competitively inhibit the transpeptidase enzyme by binding to this active site and thus inhibit crosslink formation within mucopeptide components. Similarly, chloramphenicol molecule chelates through the hydroxyl oxygen and the secondary nitrogen for its competitive inhibition of binding of m-RNA to ribosomes¹⁷. In streptomycin molecule, it is the N-methyl-L-glucosamine unit, which takes part in chelation with the metal ions through the nitrogen and the oxygen atoms^{36,37}. However, oxytetracycline molecules chelate with the metal ions through the $-\text{COCH}(\text{OH})-$ grouping, using both the oxygen atoms³⁸. The sulfa drugs use one of the two oxygen atoms of the sulfonamido (SO_2NH) group and a nitrogen atom of the heterocyclic ring systems (N-

pyridine or N-thiazole)^{57,58}. In all these drugs the active groups, mentioned above, are situated at the positions ideal for the formation of 5- or 6-membered stable chelate rings.

The substitution in the molecules with multifunctional groups^{26,29,67} or with heterocycles^{32,34,68} and/or with ether -O- atom (chelation involving this group necessary for biological activity)^{19-22,69,70} greatly increases their antibiotic activity because this increases their basic strength and/or furnishes delocalization of π -electrons over the whole chelate rings. It has been seen that if the non-coordinated hydrophobic phenyl or substituted phenyl group of amino acids is in the axial direction of the metal ion, the molecule has higher activity in consistent with the greater stability of the chelates. In general, the activity increases with increasing hydrophobicity. Further, it has been shown that although the stereoisomers have similar physical and chemical properties, but their physiological properties are different. We know, only *cis*- $\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2$ is active as a drug but not the *trans*-isomer^{71,72}. The *cis*-diamine moiety can bind groups 280 pm apart to form strain-free chelate ring, while the *trans*-isomer can be bound to groups about 400 pm apart that approach the platinum atom from opposite directions, and it is chemotherapeutically inactive.

Apparently, most receptors are proteins. The best understood structural feature of proteins is their polypeptide nature. The spacing between peptide bonds is very regular, since almost all the amino acids are linked through their α -amino and α -carboxyl groups. The distance between peptide bonds is commonly called the 'identity distance' and is equal to 3.61 Å, in a maximally extended peptide¹⁶. Studies relating various types of pharmacological activities to intramolecular distances between groupings in different series of drugs have often revealed this identity distance or some whole number multiple thereof as the spacing most readily correlated with optimum activity in a given series. The distance between functional groups of many types of drug appears to be about 5.5 Å, and, interestingly, this corresponds to the distance between two turns of an α -protein helix.

The influence of the presence of an adjacent $\text{C}=\text{C}$ bond on the protonation and metallation equilibria of the peptide bond (CONH) and the influence of the presence of COOH and phenolic OH groups in adjacent positions on the modes of metal ion coordination of the ligands has been mostly found enhancing^{65,66} as this again helps in formation of stable chelate rings and in possibility of delocalised π -bonding.

Amongst the nucleic acid bases, purine coordinates with N(7) and guanine with N(9) atoms^{73,74}, while adenine, cytosine, uracil and thymine coordinate with metal ions using their N(3) atoms^{75,76} because in these cases the distances between the coordinating groups are ideal for formation of stable chelates.

[2] Apart from the stereospecificity of the drug-receptor interaction sensitivity to specific metal ion during biocatalytic activity is also important. Each metal ion has fixed stereochemistry in a particular oxidation state and affinity for specific functional groups (active sites). This specific sensitivity seems interesting in the light of the fact that drugs influence enzyme activity and the latter depends upon the presence of specific metal ions: The selective binding patterns for a particular ligand group follows the HSAB (Hard Soft Acid Base) principle. As the chelation of a drug with the metal ion not only gives specific conformation to the drug (which may fit into the receptor site), the electronic configuration and/or *e/r*-ratio also play important part in molecular plarizability. A close correlation has been found between molecular polarizability and the extent of some biological responses⁷⁷. This probably explains why some metal chelates of the drugs (with the specific metal ions) only have enhanced bioactivity, compared to the activity of the parent drugs (Table 1).

[3] The activity of a drug apparently depends upon its concentration in the body fluids and tissues. The drug is active so long it is attached to the receptor. Hence, not only the chemical structures (and so the chemical properties), but the physical properties of the drugs also play important part in their biological activity. Chelation with metal ions gives some important properties to the drug which are helpful in their biological activity, e.g. low dissociation constant (strong metal-ligand bond), special redox potential, electron distribution, and solubilities. These properties have marked effect on the solubilities of drugs in the lipid (an important factor in the drug action) and their pharmacological transport mechanism. Because the chelation reduces the polarity of the metal ion in complexes, this increases the hydrophobic character of the metal-chelate favouring its permeation through lipid-layer of micro-organism. Attempts have been made to correlate the stability of the metal drug chelates with their antibacterial activity⁵⁷⁻⁶⁴. The studies on drug-metal ion equilibria involving specific metal ions show these interactions enthalpy characterized with high values of formation constants^{19-22,26,29,33,34,60,78} and ΔH : negative enthalpy change indicating sufficient degree of covalent character in metal-drug bonds, resulting in high lipid solubility and hence high bioavailability and antibiotic activity of the drug (Table 1). Ligands containing N and/or S containing donor atoms are most effective in this respect⁷⁸. Forces between drugs and receptors, i.e. the relative strength of the binding of drug to the receptor are thus important in deciding not only the duration of its action, but also the degree of its bioactivity.

[4] Model studies on the metal bridged drug-receptor interactions, i.e. study of ternary equilibria (mixed complexes) involving bio-metal ions with the drug as the primary ligand (L) and amino acid/or metabolite moiety as

secondary ligand (A) have indicated favoured formation of metal : drug : receptor residue 1 : 1 : 1 chelates at the physiological pH; since the values of the stability qualifying parameter, $\Delta \log K (= \log K_{MLA}^M - \log K_{ML}^M)$ obtained for the ternary complexes in these studies are generally positive or less negative than -0.6 , it shows extrastabilization of the mixed ligand complexes^{25,75,82} in consistant with their strong antibiotic activity. It has been observed that the $\Delta \log K$ values are positive if secondary ligands are O,O donors, negative if the secondary ligands are N,N donors and midway between the two if the secondary ligands are N,O donors. Intraligand interactions with drugs (hydrophobic and stacking) generally give positive $\Delta \log K$ values. In the drugs attacking DNA (e.g. tetracycline, streptomycin, chloramphenicol etc.) aromatic side-chains give positive $\Delta \log K$ due to the staking interactions between the pyrimidine ring of cytidine and phenyl ring of aromatic side-chain of amino acids.

This brief review thus provides convincing evidences in the favour of metal-chelation and formation of metal-bridged drug-receptor ternary complexes during activity of various antibiotic drugs. This has certainly catalyzed innovative strategies in developing more effective and safer antibiotic drugs, utilizing the recent experimental and theoretical developments in this area^{83,84}.

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